

HYBRID POWER GENERATION USING SOLAR AND WIND ENERGY

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Abstract:

The non-renewable energy resources are getting exhausted and the problem of global warming given huge opportunity for researchers to find out the energy crises solution. Non-Conventional energy resources such as wind energy and solar energy have been widely adopted as an alternative source of energy. In this work, an integrated solar and wind energy system were implemented aiming to produce the maximum possible output power from the available renewable energy resources such as solar irradiance and wind energy. The purpose of this project was to design a portable and low cost power system that combines both wind electric and solar electric technologies. Such project is designed efforts to develop a power solution for remote locations such as undeveloped areas and research areas as well enhance the general standard of living of individuals. For developing countries affected by natural disasters. For this reason, it is imperative to design a hybrid system that will deliver a minimum of 1,500 watts of continuous power which is enough to power a wide range of appliances and medical equipment.

Keyword: Renewable Energy, Solar energy, Windmill, Battery, PV cells.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Electricity is most needed for our day to day life. There are two ways of electricity generation either by conventional energy resources or by non-conventional energy resources. Electrical energy demand increases in word so to fulfill demand we have to generate electrical energy. Now a day's electrical energy is generated by the conventional energy resources like coal, diesel, and nuclear etc [1]. The main drawback of these sources is that it produces waste like ash in coal power plant, nuclear waste in nuclear power plant and taking care of this wastage is very costly. And it also damages he nature [2]. The nuclear waste is very harmful to human being also. The conventional energy resources are depleting day by day. Soon it will be completely vanishes from the earth so we have to find another way to generate electricity [3]. The new source should be reliable, pollution free and economical. The non-conventional energy resources should be good alternative energy resources for the conventional energy resources. There are many non-conventional energy resources like geothermal, tidal, wind, solar etc. the tidal energy has drawbacks like it can only implemented on sea shores. While geothermal energy needs very lager step to extract heat from earth. Solar and wind are easily available in all condition. The non-conventional energy resources like solar, wind can be good alternative source [4]. Solar energy has drawback that it could not produce electrical energy in rainy and cloudy season so we need to overcome this drawback we can use two energy resources so that any one of source fails other source will keep generating the electricity. And in good weather condition we can use both sources combine [5].

Renewable energy resources are primarily obtained from the nature and available in abundance. Thus, producing electricity with the use of renewable resources like Wind and Solar has been taken up in this project. A Windmill,

which rotates when there is enough wind, generates electricity owing to magnetic coupling between the rotating and stationary coil [6]. Here in this project number of horizontally rotating type of Windmill is used. Silicon based cells these are combined together to form a Solar Panel is being used in this project to obtain electrical energy [7]. Dual Power Generation combined Solar and Windmill System will bring into work to both the Solar and Windmill i.e., Wind Turbine Generator to charge a 12V Battery. The System is completely based on the renewable energy resources. The Windmill, when the sufficient amount of wind force strike on blades of windmills by this means we generate sufficient amount of power to charge a battery [8]. Similarly, the Solar Panel which is placed on a fixed panel which sets itself to maximum exposure of the daylight to generate energy enough to charge the battery. Since both of them simultaneously can work in favorable natural conditions, both can charge the battery at a faster pace than they would have individually. Thus, this project is an example how natural resources can be efficiently harnessed to produce electricity at a faster pace and cheaper rate [9].

2. RELATED WORKS:

Recent advancements in hybrid renewable energy systems integrating wind and solar power have been extensively studied to enhance efficiency and reliability in power generation. Pranoy Roy, Jiangbiao He, Tiefu Zhao, and Yash Veer Singh (2020) presented a comprehensive review of wind-solar Hybrid Renewable Energy Systems (HRES). Their work, published in IEEE, focused on power architectures, mathematical modeling, power electronic converter topologies, and design optimization algorithms. The study concluded that hybrid systems offer increased efficiency and stability in energy supply compared to standalone wind or solar systems [1].

Ahmed Amr, A. Radwan, and Yasser Abdel-Rady I. Mohamed introduced a grid-connected wind-solar cogeneration system in their IEEE paper. The system uses a permanent magnet synchronous generator-based full-scale wind turbine, and independent maximum power point tracking is employed for both wind and solar generators to maximize energy extraction. This approach ensures efficient use of renewable resources in a grid-connected [2].

A recent study by Abhishek Gupta, Abhinav Tiwari, Deepak Sharma, and Sonal Sapra discussed a dual power generation system utilizing wind and solar energy sources. This system efficiently charges a battery to store generated power, aiming to address the energy crisis by enhancing living standards in remote and disaster-affected areas. Their work highlights the potential of hybrid systems to provide reliable energy in challenging environments [3].

Nishant Jha, Deepak Prashar, Mamoon Rashid, Zeba Khanam, Amandeep Nagpal, Ahmed Alghamdi, and Sultan Alshamrani proposed an energy-efficient hybrid power system model based on solar and wind energy for integrated grids. Published in IEEE, their research suggests a dual-energy generation system that minimizes energy wastage and reduces the overall costs of electricity generation by up to 20% compared to diesel and non-grid-based systems. The system also allows a 10% annual capacity shortage, making it cost-effective and sustainable [4].

Firas B. Ismail, Norul Ilham Noruddin, and Nizar F. O. Al-Muhsen designed and developed a dual power generation system combining solar and windmill generators. Their IEEE paper implemented an integrated system comprising two solar modules and horizontally rotating wind blades. The objective was to maximize power generation from renewable resources like solar irradiance and wind energy, ensuring optimal utilization of available energy [5].

Overall, these studies underscore the significant potential of hybrid wind-solar systems in providing a stable and efficient energy supply. The integration of advanced technologies such as maximum power point tracking, power electronic converters, and sophisticated control algorithms enhances the performance and reliability of these systems. The research highlights the growing importance of hybrid renewable energy systems in addressing global energy challenges and promoting sustainable development [6]

3. PROPOSED METHOD

For design of the hybrid energy system we need to find the data as follows

A. Data required for Solar System:

- a. Annual mean daily duration of Sunshine hours
- b. Daily Solar Radiation horizontal (KWH/m²/day)

B. Data required for Wind System:

- a. Mean Annual Hourly Wind Speed (m/sec)
- b. Wind Power that can be generated from the wind turbine

Figure 1. Hybrid power generation using solar and wind energy

The basic Objective of this project is to increase the efficiency of the power generation. As the electrical power obtained by renewable energy resources is dependent upon weather. So here we are generating power from two renewable energy resources and charging the battery. The battery is getting charged more efficiently. The two renewable energy resources are solar and wind. The windmill has the maximum capacity for power generation of 12v but due to friction it is generating power up to 6v only. It is not directly connected to battery but here we have used diode. Since power flow occurs from high to low and since here power generation is up to 6v only, so the flow of power will get reversed. Instead of charging the battery windmill will take power from the battery itself. So, to overcome this problem we have used diode here. The solar panel is the second source of power generation with maximum power generating capacity of 12v. It can be monitored on multimeter that how much power is getting generated from the solar panel. Further the power generated is getting stored in the battery. The power from the battery is transferred to the loads.

3.1 SOLAR PHOTOVOLTAIC CELLS

Solar PV cells convert sunlight directly into electricity through the photovoltaic effect. They are a widely used technology for harnessing solar energy, offering several benefits such as low operating costs, minimal maintenance, and scalability.

A solar PV cell is typically made from semiconductor materials, most commonly silicon. When sunlight strikes the surface of the cell, photons from the light are absorbed by the semiconductor material, creating electron-hole pairs. These free electrons move towards the front surface of the cell, creating a flow of electric current when an external circuit is connected.

3.2 WIND TURBINES

Wind turbines convert the kinetic energy of wind into electrical energy through the use of aerodynamic blades and an electric generator. They are effective in areas with consistent and strong wind patterns.

Wind turbines consist of rotor blades, a shaft, and a generator. When wind blows, it exerts force on the blades, causing them to rotate. This rotational motion is transferred to the generator via the shaft, producing electricity.

3.3 CHARGE CONTROLLER:

Charge controller has basic function is that it control the source which is to be active or inactive. It simultaneously charge battery and also gives power to the load. The controller has over-charge protection, short-circuit protection, pole confusion protection and automatic dumpload function. It also the function is that it should vary the power as per the load demand. It add the both the power so that the load demand can fulfill. And when power is not generating it should extract power from battery and give it to the load.

4. PROPOSED CALCULATION

The total power generated by this system may be given as the addition of the power generated by the solar PV panel and power generated by the wind turbine.

Mathematically it can be represented as,

$$P_T = N_W * P_W + N_S * P_S$$

Where,

P_T is the total power generated

P_W is the power generated by wind turbines

P_S is the power generated by solar panels

N_W is the no of wind turbine

N_S is the no of solar panels used

A. Calculations Wind energy

The power generated by wind energy is given by, Power = (density of air * swept area * velocity cubed)/2

$$PW = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho (AW) (V)^3$$

Where,

P is power in watts (W)

ρ is the air density in kilograms per cubic meter (kg/m^3)

AW is the swept area by air in square meters (m^2)

V is the wind speed in meters per second (m/s).

B. Calculations for solar energy

To determine the size of PV modules, the required energy consumption must be estimated. Therefore, the power is calculated as

$$PS = \text{Ins}(t) * AS * \text{Eff}(pv)$$

Where,

Ins (t) = isolation at time t (kw/m^2)

AS = area of single PV panel (m^2)

Effpv = overall efficiency of the PV panels and dc/dc converters.

Overall efficiency is given by,

$$\text{Eff}(pv) = H * PR$$

Where,

H = Annual average solar radiation on tilted panels.

PR = Performance ratio, coefficient for losses

5. CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

Figure 2. Basic Circuit Diagram

The circuit diagram of the proposed model is shown in the above figure. The Solar-Wind hybrid system has PV (12V DC) connected to a battery. In which it stores energy. An inverter converts DC into AC (220 V, 1500 W). The wind turbine has three blades, connected to a motor/generator that generates AC output. A rectifier converts AC into DC supply. Again, battery banks store this energy. In the last stage, inverter supplies the AC signal to Load (LED).

6. SIMULATION SETUP

Figure 3. Simulation setup of hybrid power generation using MATLAB

Figure 3, illustrates a MATLAB/Simulink model of a hybrid power generation system. The system features a 100-kW photovoltaic (PV) array composed of 330 SunPower SPR-305E-WHT-D modules, which convert sunlight into DC power. The irradiance and temperature conditions affecting the PV array are simulated using a ramp-up/down irradiance block. A Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) controller optimizes the power output of the PV array, while a 5 kHz, 500V boost converter increases the DC voltage for the inverter. The boosted DC power is converted to AC using a 500V, 33*60 Hz, three-level Voltage Source Converter (VSC), which is controlled by a dedicated VSC control block to ensure proper synchronization and power quality. The AC power is then stepped up by a 100 kVA, 260V/25 kV transformer for transmission to the utility grid. The model includes various measurement blocks to monitor power, voltage, and current throughout the system, ensuring efficient operation and integration with the grid.

7. SIMULATION RESULTS

Figure 4. Simulation results of hybrid power generation (solar +wind) using MATLAB

Figure4, displays the simulation results of the hybrid power generation system depicted in Figure4, focusing on voltage and current waveforms. The top plot shows the voltage waveform (V_a), which is smooth and sinusoidal, indicating high power quality at the output of the Voltage Source Converter (VSC). The bottom plot illustrates the current waveform (I_a), which, while predominantly sinusoidal, exhibits slight distortions. These distortions might indicate minor non-idealities or harmonics in the system, common in power electronic converters. Overall, the waveforms reflect the system's effective performance in converting and delivering power to the utility grid.

8. RESULTS OF DESCRIPTIVE STATICS OF STUDY VARIABLES

Inputs	Input Voltage	Output Voltage
Solar Panel	-	12V
Wind Mill	-	10V
Inverter 100W	12V	230V 50Hz
USB Port	230V 50Hz	12V
Switch/Bulb Socket	230V 50Hz	230V 50Hz
Battery	12V	12V

Table 1. Results of descriptive statics of study variables

The table1 summarizes the input and output voltages for various components in a hybrid power generation system. Solar panels and wind mills serve as renewable energy sources, outputting 12V DC and 10V DC, respectively. An inverter takes the 12V DC from sources like solar panels or batteries and converts it to 230V AC at 50Hz, enabling the use of standard household appliances. The USB port, designed for charging or powering devices, converts the standard 230V AC to 12V DC. Switch and bulb sockets operate directly with the 230V AC at 50Hz, aligning with typical grid voltage standards. Batteries in the system are used both for storage and supply, maintaining a consistent 12V DC output. This configuration illustrates how different voltage requirements are met and managed within a hybrid system, integrating renewable energy sources with conventional electrical infrastructure to provide reliable and versatile power solutions.

9.RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Figure 5-Amount of power generated is displayed on the LCD

The image above illustrates the hybrid power generation system that integrates wind and solar energy sources to provide a reliable and efficient energy supply. The system harnesses wind energy through a wind mill and solar energy via a solar panel, which is adjusted by a servo motor for optimal sunlight exposure. The generated energy is managed by a microcontroller, which directs it to a battery for storage, ensuring energy availability even when wind or solar inputs are low. A power supply, rectifier, and regulator ensure a stable DC power source for the system. The microcontroller also interfaces with a display to provide real-time data on system performance. This setup allows for continuous monitoring and optimization of energy generation and storage, effectively combining the strengths of both renewable sources to enhance overall efficiency and reliability, making it suitable for off-grid and remote applications. And the figure shows the display screen indicating the combined voltage output from a hybrid power generation system using both solar and wind energy. The text on the screen reads "Solar + Wind Voltage: 0.54," suggesting that the system is actively measuring and displaying the voltage generated by the integration of both renewable energy.

Potential Improvements:

- **Advanced Energy Storage Solutions:** Implementing advanced battery technologies such as lithium-ion, flow batteries, or even emerging technologies like solid-state batteries.
- **Improved Solar Tracking Systems:** Implementing more sophisticated solar tracking systems, such as dual-axis trackers, and integrating AI-based tracking algorithms.
- **Wind Turbine Optimization:** Using advanced materials and designs for wind turbine blades, and integrating variable speed and pitch control mechanisms.
- **Hybrid System Simulation and Modeling:** Utilizing advanced simulation and modeling tools to design and optimize hybrid systems before deployment

10. CONCLUSION:

Hybrid solar-wind power generation systems provide a robust and efficient solution for harnessing renewable energy. By leveraging the complementary nature of solar and wind resources, these systems ensure a stable and reliable power supply. A thorough site assessment and optimal location selection are crucial to maximize energy capture and efficiency. Designing the system with the right mix of solar panels and wind turbines tailored to the site's specific conditions enhances performance. Incorporating energy storage solutions, such as batteries, is essential for maintaining a consistent power supply during low-generation periods. Sophisticated control systems enable efficient management of energy flows, optimizing output based on real-time conditions. Compliance with local regulations and standards is necessary for grid-connected systems, ensuring seamless integration and energy exchange with the grid. Construction and installation must adhere to safety and environmental protocols, followed by comprehensive testing and commissioning to validate system functionality. Continuous monitoring and proactive maintenance are vital to track performance and prevent issues, ensuring long-term reliability and efficiency. Regular evaluations against initial projections help identify areas for improvement and implement optimization strategies. Hybrid solar-wind systems offer a scalable solution for diverse energy needs, particularly in off-grid or remote locations. They significantly reduce dependence on fossil fuels and minimize greenhouse gas emissions, contributing to environmental sustainability. As renewable energy technologies advance, the adoption of hybrid systems is expected to grow, driven by the increasing demand for clean and reliable energy sources. Therefore, hybrid solar-wind power generation systems represent a promising path towards a sustainable energy future. By following a structured methodology for assessment, design, integration, and maintenance, these systems can achieve optimal performance and address both current and future energy challenges.

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